

Subgroup Resonance Self-Shielding Using an Isogeometric Analysis Spatial Discretization of the Self-Adjoint Angular Flux Equation

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ABSTRACT

A second-order self-adjoint angular flux (SAAF) formulation of the subgroup equation is presented for use with isogeometric analysis (IGA) in resonance self-shielding methods and its run time and accuracy are compared with existing first-order IGA methods. A continuous Bubnov-Galerkin isogeometric analysis spatial discretization and a discrete ordinates S_N angular discretization are used to solve the SAAF subgroup equation for a modified 'Yamamoto' benchmark consisting of a 3×3 square lattice of UOX pincells of the Rowlands benchmarks' composition. Results for multiplication factor, run time and detailed groupwise reaction rates are compared with the Monte Carlo code Serpent2 and with a previously published first-order discontinuous Bubnov-Galerkin S_N IGA subgroup formulation. Multiplication factors and run time are also compared with a collision probability (CP) formulation. Both first-order, CP and SAAF methods show agreement in eigenvalue with Serpent to a maximum error of 421 pcm, which is deemed as potentially acceptable. The difference between CP, first-order and second-order SAAF k_∞ values are found to be low, suggesting agreement between the methods and that SAAF subgroup obtains acceptable accuracy. Additionally, SAAF subgroup reaction rates show good agreement with Serpent2 and strong agreement with first-order methods. SAAF formulations are however found to have significantly longer run times than first-order or CP methods but when run time scalings are compared between CP and SAAF they tentatively favor SAAF for large problems. The results suggest continuous Galerkin IGA SAAF S_N subgroup formulations could be a promising formulation with advantages on large problems for high performance computing architectures.

Keywords: resonance self-shielding, subgroup method, self-adjoint angular flux (SAAF), isogeometric analysis (IGA), discrete ordinates (S_N)

1. INTRODUCTION TO THE SELF-ADJOINT ANGULAR FLUX EQUATION FOR THE SUBGROUP EQUATION

1.1. Resonance Self-Shielding

Resonance self-shielding (RSS) calculations are a key step in nuclear reactor lattice physics calculations. RSS methods 'condense' or average the continuously varying neutron cross-sections in energy to group constants for use in the multigroup energy discretization, the aim being to preserve observed reaction rates, avoiding the introduction of error by averaging; this is made challenging by neutron resonances [1, Ch. 4]. One prominent RSS method is the subgroup method, which has been used in many established codes including DRAGON (versions 4 and 5), APOLLO (1,2 and 3) and WIMS7 [1, Sec. 4.2]. This paper utilizes the REIGNITE code, a proprietary module for DRAGON5 which implements isogeometric analysis (IGA) [2]. As such, the subgroup formulation of DRAGON5 code [3] is used, namely the

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approach of the USS: module (with some minor changes) [1, Sec. 4.2.2.]. The full details of this method are not discussed but can be found in Sec. 4.2.4 and Sec. 4.2.5 of *Applied Reactor Physics* by Hébert [1]. This yields the following transport equation for the subgroup flux $\varphi_{k,g}$, for the subgroup k , and group g .

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \varphi_{k,g}(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega}) + \left[\Sigma_g^+(\mathbf{r}) + \Sigma_{k,g}(\mathbf{r}) \right] \varphi_{k,g}(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega}) \\ = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left\{ \Sigma_g^+(\mathbf{r}) + N^*(\mathbf{r}) \left[\sum_{\ell=1}^K \omega_{\ell,g} \sigma_{s\ell,g}^*(\mathbf{r}) \varphi_{\ell,g}(\mathbf{r}) \right] \right\} = Q_k(\mathbf{r}), \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where Σ_g^+ refers to macroscopic total cross-section of all non-resonant isotopes in group g , i.e. all isotopes other than the specific resonant isotope for which the subgroup calculation is being done, as only one isotope is considered resonant at a time. $\Sigma_{k,g}$ is the subgroup cross-section from the total cross-section probability table of the resonant isotope, N^* is the atomic density of the resonant isotope being considered and $\sigma_{s\ell,g}^*$ is the zeroth-order microscopic scattering cross-section of the resonant isotope in subgroup k which is determined from a separate probability table [4]. Note the scattering source is approximated as isotropic in angle; this introduces little error for self-shielding methods while making the equation more amenable to solving and is thus justified [1].

1.2. Isogeometric Analysis and the Motivation for Second-Order Transport Formulations

The isogeometric analysis (IGA) uses non-uniform rational B-splines (NURBS) as basis functions for a Galerkin method, allowing construction of exact geometric models as opposed to traditional approximate polynomial finite element meshes [2]. The key property of using NURBS surface basis functions in 2D problems is that quadratic or higher order NURBS can exactly represent 2D conic geometries, including circles and arbitrary sections of circles [2]. Use of such a NURBS basis removes all geometric error in the representation of a lattice geometry such as the one used in this paper, see Section 2, and thus may be advantageous for self-shielding calculations. As such, it has been applied to the hyperbolic first-order subgroup equation above (Eq. 1) by both Donegan et al. [2] and Nezondet et al. [5], using a discontinuous Bubnov-Galerkin (DBG) strategy. However, when compared to existing collision probabilities (CP) or other S_N methods, DBG IGA's extra overheads can hinder performance.

Second-order neutron transport formulations, such as even-parity or self-adjoint angular flux (SAAF) equations [6], may provide a solution to performance issues. With such an equation, a second-order elliptic PDE in space would result after taking a suitable source iteration approach which, with a continuous Bubnov-Galerkin (CBG) method, reduces to solving a symmetric positive definite (SPD) matrix $Ax = b$ problem [7]. As discussed by Latimer et al., second-order forms have the advantage of using CBG, significantly reducing degrees of freedom and allowing use of efficient preconditioned conjugate gradient algorithms [7], first-order methods generally requiring DBG solvers, which must store more nodal information and also interfacial information between elements. Geometric and algebraic hierarchical multilevel matrix iteration solution algorithms can also be employed for elliptic systems, which are the some of the most advanced and optimal solving techniques in the literature [8, 9]. Higher order spatial discretizations of elliptic PDEs can be solved efficiently on the latest exascale high performance computing (HPC) hardware architectures as demonstrated by the Center for Efficient Exascale Discretizations (CEED), leveraging parallelism and GPU computing [10]. Indeed, to reduce data motion and to maximize arithmetic intensity is currently the optimal strategy for performance on such scales; this favors higher order basis functions [10]. Hyperbolic formulations require different solution strategies which may not be as efficient on next generation hardware, depending on exactly what shape the future of computing takes.

This paper intends to provide a proof of concept of using an elliptic formulation for resonance self-shielding calculations. The SAAF equation is chosen due to its full representation of angular flux and

ease of dealing with S_N boundary conditions. An IGA CBG form of the SAAF subgroup equation will be derived and used as a solver for a set of benchmark problems. A fully optimized solver utilizing e.g. advanced multigrid techniques (etc.) will not be used, nor will the solver be applied to problems in the exascale range where advantages may be most apparent, but future work will investigate this. A comparison of run times between first- and second order forms will be provided, and the scaling of run time with problem size will be compared between CP and SAAF methods.

1.3. The Self-Adjoint Angular Flux (SAAF) Subgroup Equation

A second-order self-adjoint angular flux (SAAF) subgroup formulation is derived following the methodology of Morel & McGhee [6]. First, consider Eq. 1 written in an abridged form with group g subscript and explicit dependence omitted,

$$\hat{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \varphi_k(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega}) + [\Sigma^+ + \Sigma_k] \varphi_k(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega}) = Q_k(\mathbf{r}), \quad Q_k(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left\{ \Sigma^+(\mathbf{r}) + N^*(\mathbf{r}) \left[\sum_{\ell=1}^K \omega_\ell \sigma_{s\ell}^*(\mathbf{r}) \varphi_\ell^{\text{Prev}}(\mathbf{r}) \right] \right\}. \quad (2)$$

Note that ignoring the complexity of the source term is justified as a source iteration approach is taken, wherein the source is considered an iterating constant for each solve based on some previous iteration's flux, which is denoted as φ_k^{Prev} . Consider the re-arrangement of Eq. 2

$$\varphi_k(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega}) = -\frac{\hat{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \varphi_k}{\Sigma^+ + \Sigma_k} + \frac{Q_k(\mathbf{r})}{\Sigma^+ + \Sigma_k}. \quad (3)$$

This may be substituted into the Eq. 2 above to yield the following

$$\begin{aligned} & -\hat{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \left[\frac{1}{\Sigma_g^+(\mathbf{r}) + \Sigma_{k,g}(\mathbf{r})} \hat{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \varphi_{k,g}(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega}) \right] + [\Sigma_g^+(\mathbf{r}) + \Sigma_{k,g}(\mathbf{r})] \varphi_{k,g}(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega}) \\ & = Q_k(\mathbf{r}) - \hat{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \left[\frac{Q_k(\mathbf{r})}{\Sigma_g^+(\mathbf{r}) + \Sigma_{k,g}(\mathbf{r})} \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

This equation is known as the SAAF subgroup equation henceforth. As in regular SAAF for void or rarefied regions, the terms inversely proportionality to $\Sigma_g^+ + \Sigma_{k,g}$ may become undefined or introduce poor conditioning respectively; this is a well-known issue with second-order forms [6]. To solve the equation, an angular discretization is chosen, specifically the discrete ordinates, or S_N formulation. This implies selecting a quadrature set of N_a ordinates $\hat{\Omega}_a$ each with an associated weight W_a which are selected to accurately evaluate the scalar flux from the angular flux where $\varphi_a(\mathbf{r}) = \varphi(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega}_a)$, i.e.

$$\varphi(\mathbf{r}) = \int_{4\pi} \varphi(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega}) d^2\Omega \approx \sum_a^{N_a} W_a \varphi(\mathbf{r}, \hat{\Omega}_a) = \sum_a W_a \varphi_a(\mathbf{r}).$$

Suppressing explicit spatial dependence, this gives the S_N subgroup SAAF equation, which is the form solved in this paper, as follows

$$-\hat{\Omega}_a \cdot \nabla \left[\frac{1}{\Sigma_g^+ + \Sigma_{k,g}} \hat{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \varphi_{k,a,g} \right] + [\Sigma_g^+ + \Sigma_{k,g}] \varphi_{k,a,g} = Q_k - \hat{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \left[\frac{Q_k}{\Sigma_g^+ + \Sigma_{k,g}} \right]. \quad (5)$$

1.3.1. Boundary Conditions

The S_N subgroup equation's (Eq. 1) boundary conditions (BCs) are the same as those for first-order S_N neutron transport formulations. BCs are prescribed for incoming angular fluxes, i.e. all portions of the

boundary surface ∂V , of the domain V , for a given $\hat{\Omega}_a$ on which neutrons are incoming or 'grazing' (i.e. exactly parallel to the surface) [6, 7]. This subsection of the surface is denoted ∂V_a^- . Standard reflective incoming BCs are considered throughout this paper.

The SAAF subgroup equation (Eq. 4) obeys these same BCs for the ∂D_a^- surface [6]; however, as a second-order formulation, an additional second boundary condition is required. For this purpose, BCs are considered on the outgoing angular flux as in Morel & McGhee [6]. This can be formulated from an S_N form of Eq. 3, for the outgoing boundary surface subsection for a given $\hat{\Omega}_a$ denoted ∂V_a^+ , as

$$\varphi_{k,a,g}(\mathbf{r}) = -\frac{\hat{\Omega}_a \cdot \nabla \varphi_{k,a,g}(\mathbf{r})}{\Sigma_g^+(\mathbf{r}) + \Sigma_{k,g}(\mathbf{r})} + \frac{Q_{k,g}(\mathbf{r})}{\Sigma_g^+(\mathbf{r}) + \Sigma_{k,g}(\mathbf{r})}, \quad \mathbf{r} \in \partial V_a^+. \quad (6)$$

1.4. Weak Form of the Subgroup SAAF Equation and Continuous Galerkin Formulation

To use Galerkin methods, one must first find the weak or integral form of the SAAF subgroup equation. The full detailed derivation of a weak form will not be given here. Consider a test function $w(\mathbf{r})$, which is chosen in the total domain spatial domain V to be in the Sobolev space $W_2^1(V)$. Similarly, assume a trial solution for φ exists in that same space. With multiplication of Eq. 4 by $w(\mathbf{r})$, integration over V and, with application of the Green's first identity, the weak form is thus obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_e^{N_e} \int_{V_e} dV_e \left(\frac{1}{\Sigma_{e,g}^+ + \Sigma_{e,k,g}} \left[\hat{\Omega}_a \cdot \nabla \varphi_{k,a,g}(\mathbf{r}) - Q_{k,g} \right] \left[\hat{\Omega}_a \cdot \nabla w(\mathbf{r}) \right] + \left[(\Sigma_{e,g}^+ + \Sigma_{e,k,g}) \varphi_{k,a,g}(\mathbf{r}) - Q_{k,g}(\mathbf{r}) \right] w(\mathbf{r}) \right) \\ + \int_{\partial V_e} dS_e \left(\frac{\hat{\Omega}_a \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}}{\Sigma_{e,g}^+ + \Sigma_{e,k,g}} \left[Q_{k,g}(\mathbf{r}) - \hat{\Omega}_a \cdot \nabla \varphi_{k,a,g}(\mathbf{r}) \right] w(\mathbf{r}) \right) = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

For this IGA implementation each non-zero knot span is equivalent to an element and the mesh is defined such that there is one element per NURBS surface. Cross-sections are constant within an element and the domain of each element V_e satisfies $V = V_1 \cup V_2 \cup \dots \cup V_{N_e}$ where N_e is the number of elements. To solve this weak form with IGA, a discretization of the test and trial Sobolev space is considered using, for each element e , the spatial NURBS basis functions associated with the NURBS surface corresponding to the element, see [2], giving

$$\varphi_{k,a,g}(\mathbf{r} \in V_e) = \sum_i^{N_b} R_i^e(\mathbf{r}) \varphi_{k,a,g,i}^e \quad w(\mathbf{r} \in V_e) = \sum_j^{N_b} R_j^e(\mathbf{r}) w_j^e \quad Q_{k,g}(\mathbf{r} \in V_e) = \sum_i^{N_b} R_i^e(\mathbf{r}) Q_{k,g,i}^e \quad (8)$$

where the superscript p is omitted from R and the superscript e refers to the element considered. The equation for $Q_{k,g}$ can be understood from Eq. 2, where the basis arises from the spatial discretization of a previous source iteration's flux $\varphi_{k,g}^{\text{Prev}}(\mathbf{r})$ (which is identical to that of the current iteration). This yields the spatially discretised S_N SAAF form below, where the subscripts k, a, g are suppressed for clarity

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{e=1}^{N_e} \int_{V_e} dV_e \left[\frac{1}{\Sigma_e^+ + \Sigma_e} \left(\left[\hat{\Omega}_a \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{N_b} \nabla R_i^e(\mathbf{r}) \varphi_i^e - \sum_{i=1}^{N_b} R_i^e(\mathbf{r}) Q_i^e \right] \left[\hat{\Omega}_a \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{N_b} \nabla R_j^e(\mathbf{r}) w_j^e \right] \right) \right. \\ \left. + \left[(\Sigma_e^+ + \Sigma_e) \sum_{i=1}^{N_b} R_i^e(\mathbf{r}) \varphi_i^e - \sum_{i=1}^{N_b} R_i^e(\mathbf{r}) Q_i^e \right] \sum_{j=1}^{N_b} R_j^e(\mathbf{r}) w_j^e \right] \\ + \int_{\partial V_e} dS_e \left[\frac{\hat{\Omega}_a \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}}{\Sigma_e^+ + \Sigma_e} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_b} R_i^e(\mathbf{r}) Q_i^e - \hat{\Omega}_a \cdot \sum_{i=1}^{N_b} \nabla R_i^e(\mathbf{r}) \varphi_i^e \right) \sum_{j=1}^{N_b} R_j^e(\mathbf{r}) w_j^e \right] = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Figure 1. (Left) IGA mesh used for self-shielding (Right) Mesh used for Collision Probabilities self-shielding solve or flux solve.

These summation products can be written as a matrix in the local element applied to a vector of fluxes and the w_j unknowns can be factored out [2]. Element matrices can be combined using the connectivity of the mesh to construct a global matrix as in Latimer et al. [7], enforcing continuity at the interface between adjacent elements and leading to a continuous Bubnov-Galerkin formulation. Surface integral terms of interior elements cancel and boundary conditions are easily enforced [7].

2. BENCHMARKING STRATEGY AND RESULTS

Numerical results are presented for a modified ‘Yamamoto’ benchmark [11]. This was chosen as its asymmetry poses a challenging flux shape, which it was hoped the high-order flux representation of IGA could solve well. Calculations make use of a SHERM-295 JEFF 3.3 ‘DRAGLIB’ library produced using PyNJOY 2012 in conjunction with NJOY 2016.66. JEFF 3.3 ACE files were obtained from the OECD-NEA distribution. Results were obtained in the REIGNITE module for DRAGON5 using the IGA mesh specified in Fig. 1 with the SAAF subgroup equation used as the underlying solver in a CALENDF 3 PT USS: resonance self-shielding calculation. An S_8 level symmetric quadrature was used with a quadratic NURBS basis for this solve. The DRAGON5 FLU: solve used for k_∞ calculations was a collision probabilities solve with the SYBILT: module with the mesh specified in Fig. 1 with options MAXR 225 QUA2 20 3 DP01 MAXZ 200000 with tracking generated by the SALT: module with options ALLG and TSPC 12 55.0 REND. Reflective BCs are used. Specifications of the pincells can be found in the Rowlands et al. benchmark technical report, see PWR UOX Cases 1 to 4 [12]. The Serpent2 Monte-Carlo code was used with 200000 neutron population for 2000 cycles with 100 inactive.

Table I shows the k_∞ values for various subgroup solvers with Serpent2 benchmark values. A DBG IGA S_N first-order solver, a CBG IGA S_N SAAF solver and a CP solver. Fig. 2 compares the spatially-integrated group-wise reaction rates in the resonant energy region for the U-238 (n, γ) reaction between Serpent2, CBG and DBG subgroup methods. Figure 3 compares how the run time scales per element between SAAF and collision probability implementations.

Figure 2. Graph showing the difference in reaction rates between first-order and SAAF formulations for radiative capture in U-238.

Table I. UOX k_{∞} values for Rowlands 3x3 Lattice 295 Group Benchmarks. Errors between the first-order subgroup, SAAF subgroup and CP subgroup cases and the implicit Monte Carlo k_{∞} are presented in parentheses.

	UOX Pin 1 k_{eff}	Run Time/s	UOX Pin 2 k_{eff}	Run Time/s	UOX Pin 3 k_{eff}	Run Time/s	UOX Pin 4 k_{eff}	Run Time/s
Serpent								
ANALOG	1.34776 ± 5 pcm	-	1.38462 ± 5 pcm	-	1.36667 ± 5 pcm	-	1.38655 ± 5 pcm	-
IMPLICIT	1.34772 ± 2 pcm	-	1.38459 ± 2 pcm	-	1.36671 ± 2 pcm	-	1.38662 ± 2 pcm	-
REIGNITE First-Order DBG-IGA-SN								
CALENDF	1.34816 (44 pcm)	617	1.38194 (-265 pcm)	670	1.36408 (-263 pcm)	627	1.38291 (-371 pcm)	643
REIGNITE Second-Order CBG-IGA-SAAF-SN								
CALENDF	1.34783 (11 pcm)	8622	1.38145 (-314 pcm)	9714	1.36356 (-315 pcm)	9917	1.38241 (-421 pcm)	11193
REIGNITE Collision Probabilities								
CALENDF	1.34830 (58 pcm)	193	1.38223 (-236 pcm)	191	1.36441 (-230 pcm)	187	1.38322 (-340 pcm)	185

Figure 3. Graphs comparing the run time per element between subgroup solves with SAAF or collision probability (CP) solvers. Lines are shown for each UOX case and show how run time scales with the number of elements, comparing 2x2, 3x3 and 4x4 forms of the used benchmark. Run times for the 'USS' module of DRAGON5 are shown.

3. CONCLUSIONS

To conclude, the CBG IGA SAAF subgroup method was found to demonstrate comparable accuracy to both first-order DBG IGA subgroup and CP subgroup implementations in k_{∞} , and reaction rates. This can be seen from the comparing of the k_{∞} values, which agree to 31-85 pcm depending on the case. Considering the inherent error in subgroup methods, this suggests a good agreement between the methods. This is further supported by reaction rate data, which, for the key example reaction and isotope of U-238 (n, γ), agrees between first-order and SAAF forms on the order of 0-1% in energy. k_{∞} agreement between REIGNITE and Serpent2 was mixed, with roughly 200-400 pcm errors; however, acceptable errors were seen in comparing the U-238 radiative capture rates between Serpent2 and REIGNITE, with error being roughly 0-5%. Overall, considering the presence of many compensating errors and the fundamental limitations of comparing deterministic and Monte Carlo methods' rates and eigenvalues, the level of agreement is probably acceptable but additional verification should be done, including a refinement study in space, angle and energy for both the resonance self-shielding and eigenvalue solves.

The results give strong support to SAAF subgroup being an accurate alternative to first-order subgroup for IGA-based resonance self-shielding but investigating the run times for the benchmark show first-order outperforms SAAF by a factor of about approx. 10-20, which itself is outperformed by CP by a factor of approx 3-4. This suggests SAAF cannot provide the required performance to compete with first-order IGA and CP methods. However, the investigation of the run time scaling of CP vs. SAAF indicates that the run time per element remains relatively constant for SAAF whereas a roughly linear relationship is observed for CP. This could be because the matrix solves in CP are dense but in SAAF are sparse. The results imply SAAF would out-compete CP at over approx. 5000 elements, but interface current methods and others may be more competitive at such scales. Fully optimized SAAF solvers should be compared versus a wide selection of methods in future work to reach a definitive conclusion but this does suggest the SAAF subgroup method may have promise for large self-shielding problems.

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